

Public acceptance of methane-reducing feed additives as a pathway to enhancing dairy farming sustainability

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Supplementary material

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Supplementary Table 1. Statements that were considered as part of citizens' attitude factors in this study.

Attitudes statements	Factor
<p>I have visited a farm and seen first-hand how cattle are raised.</p> <p>I understand the role of microbiota in human health and well-being.</p> <p>I understand the benefits and challenges associated with the food production and sustainability in the livestock sector.</p>	Familiarity with farming and microbiome
<p>It is important for me to consume food products that are safe for me.</p> <p>I take the time to read the labels and packaging information (e.g. allergens) to ensure food I purchase is safe to consume.</p> <p>I believe that food producers have an ethical responsibility to provide safe food products to consumers.</p>	Food safety
<p>I consider the environmental impact of a product before making a purchase</p> <p>I frequently recycle and make an effort to reduce my waste</p> <p>I frequently buy products that are labelled as antibiotic-free</p> <p>I try to reduce my carbon footprint by walking, biking, or taking public transit when possible</p>	Environmental awareness
<p>I actively seek out information about animal welfare standards of companies before purchasing animal derived products.</p> <p>I am willing to pay more for products that are produced using high animal welfare practices.</p> <p>I support animal welfare organizations and donate to their causes.</p>	Animal welfare
<p>I prioritize buying organic food, even if it is more expensive.</p> <p>I am willing to pay more for products that are sustainably sourced and produced.</p> <p>I am willing to pay more for food produced using high animal welfare standards.</p> <p>I am willing to pay a premium price for food products that are guaranteed to be free from harmful contaminants and residues.</p>	Conscientious consumption preferences
<p>I feel that consuming dairy products is necessary for balanced nutrition and healthy life.</p> <p>I feel that it is important to purchase dairy products to support the dairy industry and local farmers.</p> <p>Consuming dairy products is a traditional and cultural practice that should be continued.</p>	Cultural perspective of consuming dairy products

The Survey

To whom it may concern,

We would like to invite you to participate in a survey asking about your views and opinions with regards to innovative practices in dairy and beef production. The data collected from this survey will be used as part of the HoloRuminant research project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101000213. Your response will help in designing the future development of dairy and beef production in Europe.

It takes about 15 minutes to respond to the survey. Your participation in this survey is voluntary. Your data and responses will be anonymous and managed in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (2016/679). The basis for this survey is the performance of a public interest task requiring your consent. The results of this study will be published in a way that no individual respondent can be identified. If you wish to have more information about the study, please find our contact information at <https://holoruminant.eu/contacts/>

	Yes	No
Informed consent: The purpose of the study has been presented to me. I agree to participate in this study. I agree that my responses can be used by the HoloRuminant project. I have the right not to answer any of the questions and to withdraw from the survey at any time without having to explain why. I understand that anonymised data cannot be erased after the survey has been completed.		

Half of the sample in each country responds to questions in part A and the other half to questions in part B. All respondents answer to questions in parts C and D. Questions in section A and B include a multichoice question (strongly agree strongly disagree) and an open-ended field where the respondent can explain his/her choice if she/he wants to do so.

Part A

A1. After reading the information, to what extent do you agree that the following intervention is acceptable? Please select only one option.

Intervention 1	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	I don't know
Adding algae or seaweed extracts to the feed to reduce dairy cow methane emissions.						
Using Algae and seaweed extracts as feed additives to reduce dairy cow methane emissions can help to mitigate the environmental impact of dairy farming. By including certain feed additives to the cow's diet, it is possible to alter the microorganisms in the cow's gut and reduce the amount of methane produced.						
Could you please explain your reasoning behind your choice? (if applicable):						

A2. After reading the information, to what extent do you agree that the following intervention is acceptable? Please select only one option..

Intervention 2	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	I don't know
Adding plant-based oils or fats to the feed to reduce dairy cow methane emissions						
Using plant-based oils and fats as feed additives to reduce dairy cow methane emissions can help to mitigate the environmental impact of dairy farming. By including certain feed additives to the cow's diet, it is possible to alter the microorganisms in the cow's gut and reduce the amount of methane produced.						
Could you please explain your reasoning behind your choice? (if applicable):						

A3. After reading the information, to what extent do you agree that the following intervention is acceptable? Please select only one option.

Intervention 3	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	I don't know
Adding chemical additives to reduce dairy cow methane emissions.						
Using chemical additives, such as 3-nitrooxypropanol, as feed additives to reduce dairy cow methane emissions can help to mitigate the environmental impact of dairy farming. By including certain feed additives to the cow's diet, it is possible to alter the microorganisms in the cow's gut and reduce the amount of methane produced.						
Could you please explain your reasoning behind your choice? (if applicable):						

A4. Please rate how helpful was the previously provided information on the potential impacts of the interventions t when evaluating the interventions. Please select one option.

	Extremely helpful	Very helpful	Moderately helpful	Slightly helpful	Not at all helpful

Part B

B1. After reading the information on impacts, to what extent do you agree that the following intervention is acceptable? Please select only one option.

Intervention 1	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	I don't know
Adding algae or seaweed extracts to the feed to reduce dairy cow methane emissions.						
Using Algae and seaweed extracts as feed additives to reduce dairy cow methane emissions can help to mitigate the environmental impact of dairy farming. By including certain feed additives to the cow's diet, it is possible to alter the microorganisms in the cow's gut and reduce the amount of methane produced.						
Criteria	Possible impacts					
Animal health and welfare	No significant effect					
The quality of milk and meat products	Residues in milk, but at minimal levels.					
Environmental effect	Reduction of methane emissions by 30 to 50%					
Effect on production	Feeding cost increase, No impact on labour costs. Difficult to impossible in pasture-based systems.					
Cost of milk and dairy products for consumers	The rise in feed costs increases milk prices.					
Could you please explain your reasoning behind your choice? (if applicable):						

B2. After reading the information on impacts, to what extent do you agree that the following intervention is acceptable? Please select only one option.

Intervention 6	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	I don't know
Adding plant-based oils or fats to the feed to reduce dairy cow methane emissions						
Using plant-based oils and fats as feed additives to reduce dairy cow methane emissions can help to mitigate the environmental impact of dairy farming. By including certain feed additives to the cow's diet, it is possible to alter the microorganisms in the cow's gut and reduce the amount of methane produced.						
Criteria	Possible impacts					
Animal health and welfare	No known negative effects if fats and oils are less than 5 % of cow's feed intake					
The quality of milk and meat products	May have small (positive) effects on human health					
Environmental effect	Reduction of methane emissions by 5 to 15%					
Effect on production	Feeding cost increase, May effect labour costs. Difficult to impossible in pasture-based systems.					
Cost of milk and dairy products for consumers	The rise in feed costs increases milk prices.					
Could you please explain your reasoning behind your choice? (if applicable):						

B3. After reading the information on impacts, to what extent do you agree that the following intervention is acceptable? Please select only one option.

Intervention 3	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	I don't know
Adding chemical additives to the feed to reduce dairy cow methane emissions.						
Using chemical additives, such as 3-nitrooxypropanol, as feed additives to reduce dairy cow methane emissions can help to mitigate the environmental impact of dairy farming. By including certain feed additives to the cow's diet, it is possible to alter the microorganisms in the cow's gut and reduce the amount of methane produced.						
Criteria	Possible impacts					
Animal health and welfare	No impact known to date.					
The quality of milk and meat products	No known risk. Research is currently being carried out to identify possible effects.					
Environmental effect	Reduction of methane emissions by around 33%					
Effect on production	Feeding cost increase. May affect labour costs. Difficult to impossible in grass-based systems.					
Cost of milk and dairy products for consumers	The rise in feed costs increases milk prices.					
Could you please explain your reasoning behind your choice? (if applicable):						

B4. Please rate how helpful the previously provided information on the potential impacts of the interventions was when evaluating the interventions. Please select one option.

	Extremely helpful	Very helpful	Moderately helpful	Slightly helpful	Not at all helpful

Part C.

C1. To what extent do you agree with the statements below? Please select one option in each row.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I have visited a farm and seen first-hand how cattle are raised.					
I understand the role of microbiota in human health and well-being.					
I understand the benefits and challenges associated with the food production and sustainability in the livestock sector.					

C2. To what extent do you agree with the statements below? Please select one option in each row.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
It is important for me to consume food products that are safe for me.					
I am confident that the controls of competent authorities ensure food safety.					
I take the time to read the labels and packaging information (e.g. allergens) to ensure food I purchase is safe to consume.					
I believe that food producers have an ethical responsibility to provide safe food products to consumers.					
The use of antibiotics to treat farm animals is a risk to human health.					

C3. To what extent do you agree with the statements below? Please select one option in each row.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I consider the environmental impact of a product before making a purchase					
I frequently recycle and make an effort to reduce my waste					
I frequently buy products that are labelled as antibiotic-free					
I try to reduce my carbon footprint by walking, biking, or taking public transit when possible					
I actively participate in community initiatives and volunteering.					

C4. To what extent do you agree with the statements below? Please select one option in each row.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I actively seek out information about animal welfare standards of companies before purchasing animal derived products.					
I am willing to pay more for products that are produced using high animal welfare practices.					
I support animal welfare organizations and donate to their causes.					

C5. To what extent do you agree with the statements below? Please select one option in each row.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I always try to find the lowest prices when buying food.					
I am willing to wait for sales or promotions to buy food in order to save money.					
I prioritize buying organic food, even if it is more expensive.					
I am willing to pay more for products that are sustainably sourced and produced.					
I am willing to pay more for food produced using high animal welfare standards.					
I am willing to pay a premium price for food products that are guaranteed to be free from harmful contaminants and residues.					

C6. To what extent do you agree with the statements below? Please select one option in each row.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I feel that consuming dairy products is necessary for balanced nutrition and healthy life.					
I feel that it is important to purchase dairy products to support the dairy industry and local farmers.					
Consuming dairy products is a traditional and cultural practice that should be continued.					
Many of my friends or relatives have told me that consuming dairy products is ethically unacceptable.					
Many of my friends or relatives have told me that consuming dairy products is environmentally unsustainable.					

C7. How concerned are you about the statements below? Please select one option in each row.

	1=Extremely concerned	2	3	4	5=Not concerned at all
Antibiotic resistance because of the use of antibiotics in farm animals.					
Antibiotic residues in foods.					
The climate emissions originating from dairy production.					
Whether or not minimum animal welfare standards are met in dairy farming.					
Calves not being able to perform natural social behaviours such as suckling and being with their dam.					
The naturalness of practices applied in dairy production.					
Whether sufficient measures are taken to mitigate disease outbreaks in farm animals.					

Part D.

<p>D1. How old are you?</p>		
<p>D2. How many persons are there in your household?</p>	Under 12 years old	
	12 to 20 years old	
	21 to 65 years old	
	Above 65 years old	
	Male	
<p>D3. What is your gender?</p>	Female	
	Another response	
	Choose not to disclose	
<p>D4. Which of the following best describes your highest education level attained?</p>	Less than primary education	
	Primary education	
	Secondary education	
	Vocational education	
	University education	
<p>D5. What is your yearly household income before tax?</p>	€0-€10 000	
	€10 001 - €20 000	
	€20 001 - €40 000	
	€40 001 - €60 000	
	€60 001 - €80 000	
	€80 001 - €100 000	
	€100 001 - €150 000	
	€150 001 or more	
<p>D6. Which of the below describes your dietary choices? <i>Select all that apply</i></p>	I eat meat	
	I eat eggs	
	I eat fish	
	I eat dairy products	
	I am vegetarian	
	I am vegan	
<p>D7. How would you describe where you live?</p>	City centre	

	Town or suburb	
	Rural area	
D8. What is your employment status? <i>Select all that apply</i>	Employed full-time	
	Employed part-time	
	Retired	
	Homemaker	
	Self-employed	
	Student	
	Unemployed	
	Other	